

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING PHYSICS TO MEDICAL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The qualities of a graduate of a higher educational institution should allow him to work successfully in the chosen professional field, have social, personal and general cultural qualities that contribute to his social mobility and stability in the labor market.

Key words: Digital technology, professional, physics, modular system, research objects, algorithm.

РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ФИЗИКЕ СТУДЕНТОВ-МЕДИКОВ

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Аннотация

Качества выпускника высшего учебного заведения должны позволять ему успешно работать в выбранной профессиональной сфере, обладать социальными, личностными и общекультурными качествами, способствующими его социальной мобильности и стабильности на рынке труда.

Ключевые слова: Цифровые технологии, профессионал, физика, модульная система, объекты исследования, алгоритм.

TIBBIYOT TALABALARIGA FIZIKANI O'QITISHDA RAQAMLI TEKNOLOGIYANING ROLI

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Annotatsiya: Oliy ta'lim muassasasi bitiruvchisining fazilatlari unga tanlagan professional sohada muvaffaqiyatli ishlashga imkon berishi, ijtimoiy harakatchanligi va mehnat bozorida barqarorligiga hissa qo'shadigan ijtimoiy, shaxsiy va umumiy madaniy fazilatlarga ega bo'lishi kerak.

Kalit so'zlar: Raqamli texnologiyalar, professional, fizika, modulli tizim, tadqiqot obyektlari, algoritmi.

Introduction

In solving this problem, an important role belongs to the physics course. Physics is the basis of the general educational training of a specialist [1, 2]. It has a number of features that allow students to develop logic, rationality and systematic thinking. For students of medical

universities, physics, including digital technology, is necessary for the formation of basic ideas about the functioning of human body systems and for the meaningful application of these ideas in future medical practice. Physics is being introduced into medicine at an increasingly accelerated pace: laser surgery, ultrasound examination of soft tissues, magnetic resonance imaging, X-ray diagnostics, operations using a gamma scalpel, etc. [3, 4].

Methods

Mastering the physics course should precede studying anatomy, physiology, biochemistry, microbiology and virology, hygiene, radiation diagnostics, etc. But, unfortunately, first-year students are not able to fully understand the importance of knowledge of physics for the future practical activity of a doctor. In this regard, it is necessary to increase the motivation of students to study the physics course. Justification by the teacher of the interdisciplinary links of physics with clinical disciplines will allow the first-year student to see the importance of the acquired knowledge of physics for studying clinical disciplines. Thus, the educational process of a medical university is supposed to implement an integrated-modular teaching of physics.

Results

Classes at a medical university are conducted according to a modular system. Each module consists of two or three laboratory and/or practical work on related topics. Each laboratory or practical work contains all the components of the educational cycle: goal, objectives, necessary devices and equipment, research objects, algorithm for performing the work, a list of used and additional literature, as well as test tasks. Testing is used to diagnose the level of students' training and monitor their academic achievements. Testing allows us to judge the effectiveness of the learning process and make changes to improve the content of the physics course modules and their methodological support. A set of requirements for knowledge, skills and abilities has been developed for each module. It should be noted that physical and medical equipment is used to perform laboratory work. Using physical devices, students study the mechanisms of various phenomena and physical laws in individual sections of physics. These are the laws of mechanics, geometric and physical optics, acoustics, hydrodynamics and hemodynamics, electrical phenomena and laws of thermodynamics, laws of interaction of radiation with matter, conversion of one type of energy into another, radioactivity and dosimetry, etc. Of course, in physics classes in a medical institution, the emphasis is on the use of medical equipment. Medical equipment is used to practice working skills in an atmosphere close to real clinical practice. Lectures are held for each section of physics.

Analysis

The number of lecture hours for the medical and pediatric faculties differs, is limited by the curriculum, but is insufficient for a detailed presentation of the material [1]. For independent preparation, students are offered an electronic methodological manual. There are a number of methodologically and scientifically substantiated provisions in the study of any subject, including physics in a medical university: - the competence of the teacher and methodological approaches to the presentation of the material; - a trusting, equal, respectful attitude towards students; - a dialogue between the teacher and students and the presence of feedback.

Discussions

Currently, diagnostic studies of varying degrees of complexity and the safest surgical interventions can only be carried out using modern technical devices developed and maintained by physicists. A doctor must understand the physical laws and principles underlying the operation of medical equipment and correctly interpret the results of a diagnostic study. Thus, when forming a modern concept of teaching physics in higher medical educational institutions, it is necessary to focus on the ultimate goal - training highly qualified specialists with deep knowledge and who can creatively approach problem solving. The interaction between medicine and physics allows us to study the nature of physical processes, the causes of pathologies and acquire skills in working with medical equipment. The physics course, along with its fundamental nature, has a medical focus, integrated with clinical disciplines, which is a powerful motivation for students to study physics.

Conclusions

Physics and medicine are closely related sciences: many of the most important discoveries in the field of physics were made by doctors. It is at the junction of sciences that the most amazing discoveries occur.

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